

Classification of research articles for a VIVO-based research information platform

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Abstract

Research information facilitates the search and retrieval of the research data and outputs by increasing the accuracy of the search results, which saves the user a lot of time in finding crucial information for a field of research. The search process is improved even further when the research information are classified under specific academic categories and linked using ontologies.

Keywords: VIVO, Research information, NLP, Classification, Ontologies

Introduction

The Berlin University Alliance (BUA) aims in a broader context at motivating and promoting the cooperation of researchers across disciplinary and institutional boundaries. The project "research information platform with VIVO" funded by the BUA was established to exhibit this cooperation digitally. Showcasing the research expertise, activities, and outputs within the BUA requires not only a research information platform, but also a mapping, linking, and visualization of the curated information. The online presentation of research, research units and expertise has the goal of boosting visibility and findability, link and structure research activities, and facilitate external collaborations [1, 2]. This is achieved by connecting research projects and outputs using ontologies under browsing categories and by relating search results through categorization and vocabularies. The process of capturing research information demands time and effort, thus achieving this goal should be relying on highly automated processes with the least possible effort from researchers themselves.

The project, as shown by the diagram of Figure 1, relies on research information being released and imported to a data processing server for the data to be cleaned, harmonized, and classified. The standardized research information is stored in a database, allowing for federation and distribution of the data into a VIVO-server dedicated for the entire alliance. The platform shows lists of research projects, outputs of different types, including books and papers, BUA organizations, events, and researchers. These are linked and related by the use of specific ontologies suitable for the alliance member universities. These ontologies represent the organizational structures as well as disciplinary and interdisciplinary research field vocabularies. They also are based on national standards describing the domain of academic research. These are linked together through a developed ontologies of the organigramme, disciplinary and interdisciplinary research vocabulary, and format standards. A diagram depicting the ontologies developed for the BUA research information platform is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: A diagram for the BUA-VIVO project main milestones.

Figure 2: Ontologies and vocabulary used to link research units and entities.

Ontology and vocabulary

VIVO is an open source software based on open linked data, which requires building ontologies that connect different research units and entities in a wide network of research information. An ontology is a formal representation of concepts within a specific domain, the academic domain in our case, such that they can semantically and structurally relate and connect research entities. VIVO was originally developed with ontologies representing the American academic domain; therefore, we extended the ontologies and developed new ones to represent the German academic and structural domain. A machine must understand these semantic relations in a broad context to be capable of automating the connection, classification, and discovering of research information; therefore vocabularies (Research Disciplines, interdisciplinary research fields) are used to classify and disambiguate ontology

entities. This will ensure consistent understanding across different organizational and research structures and improve the discoverability and depiction of interdisciplinary cooperation across institutions and research fields, as shown in Figure 2. A detailed segment of the ontology of organization and vocabulary is shown in Figure 3. All information about the developed BUA upper ontology and extensions are found in the project repositories hosted by GitHub.

Figure 3: A diagram depicting the structures of the organization, project, and **vocabulary ontologies**

Classification of research information

The VIVO software includes a tool, which links article metadata stored in the VIVO-Database to the respective academic disciplines identified under the publishing journals. The result is displayed in a map of science, as shown in Figure 4. The BUA project aimed at broadening the scope of those classifications by including not only the academic articles but all kinds of research output as well as abstracts or descriptions of academic projects. The classification vocabularies and the classified information would be available in the VIVO system and any newly installed instance.

To include and link academic disciplines, subject matters, and interdisciplinary research fields, we developed an approach to categorize abstracts, full text documents and project descriptions using natural language processing (NLP). As a training corpus, a large collection of archived research papers was semantically and logically processed page by page. Sentence structure and meanings were analyzed, the essential meanings were extracted and subject matters were assigned by weighting the most relevant words. This process is context

sensitive and thus able to distinguish between different meanings of specific terms. Even homonyms could be resolved this way.

The list of academic disciplines [B2FIND](#) contains 336 categories and was created within the framework of the European collaborative data infrastructure project [EUDAT](#). The list is structured in four layers, the first contains five main research domains: humanities, social and behavioral sciences, life sciences, natural sciences, and engineering sciences. The structure tree splits from the first abstract layer into more specific categories under each discipline.

Figure 4: Map of science showing the disciplines which are central within a research project under a cluster of excellence.

Classification method and Validation

For training and testing, we used 20.000 research documents openly available on the [edoc-server](#) of the Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. In some cases, they provide keywords and DDC (Dewey Decimal Classification) categories assigned by the authors, which could be used to support in the classification and testing stages. However, the data corpus is voluminous and highly unbalanced, hence some specific disciplinary categories are abundantly represented while others are barely covered. The corpus is also heterogeneous, multilingual, and covering a wide range of topics. To our knowledge, there is no other reliable reference corpus of EUDAT classified texts available to date.

Figure 5: The classification approach

In order to classify each of these documents under the disciplinary categories, we developed the approach shown in Figure 5. It comprises of two stages: the Pre-Classification and Training and Testing. For each of the 336 categories, we created an extensive list of weighted keywords based on semantic similarities within the category itself. Each document is queried page by page for the keywords of each category, see Figure 6 (left panel). A weighted sum is calculated for the recognized keywords. If the weighted sum exceeds multiple fixed and variable thresholds, the corresponding category is assigned to the document. A result of the pre-classification of one document is shown in Figure 6 (right panel). The figure shows three dominant categories – medicine, psychology, and social sciences –, and several minor categories. In this case the document will be automatically assigned the three dominant categories. The process is repeated for all documents. If after the complete processing, a category is not assigned to at least fifty documents, it does not pass to the next stage, since the available documents will not be sufficient to train the machine learning model.

Figure 6: Pre-classification steps and application results of classifying one research document.

In the next stage, the categories, keywords, and documents are imported to the software-server, which is provided by Kairntech, an external service provider. A Keras-based machine learning model is trained and tuned using 80% of the documents, and the testing is done using the remaining 20%. For validation we used internal and external datasets to determine the accuracy of the resulting models. In a first approach the text of 9.000 documents was vectorized as were the keywords and categories to look for similarities within the semantic space. In this specific run, we used the upper layer in the B2FIND Discipline tree, which contains five categories.

Figure 7: The precision of classification results under five major disciplines using a dataset of 9000 documents.

The trained model assigns categories to the documents and we inspected their quality scores (precision, recall and f-score). The precision of the classification results are shown in Figure 7. We notice in Figure 7 that the model can best differentiate humanities and life sciences. The quality of the classification drops for natural and engineering sciences, since they often share subjects and terms and hence have overlap within and between their semantic spaces. In a similar manner, Social and Behavioral Sciences include the topics of Psychology and Education. Keywords that describe Psychology share a lot of their semantic space with medicine, while the topic Education often shares its semantic space with the actual topic taught. Since those overlaps in meaning are inherent in the EUDAT categories, false predictions can only be avoided by larger training datasets. Therefore, we trained the machine learning model again using a full set of 19.000 documents. This time all 336 categories were included in the testing. The quality analysis of the output is shown in Figure 8.

Precision is defined as the ratio between the number of correctly predicted categories and the sum of correct predictions and false predictions while recall is defined as the ratio of correctly predicted categories and the sum of correct predictions and missed predictions. The F-Score is a value combining both measures into a single number. In V1, the software calculated the metrics considering each category independently. V2 recalculated the metrics taking into account the relationships between the categories and ignoring inheritance errors. This is the most realistic measure of the true strength of a model. The premise for V3 was, that an incomplete prediction is not necessarily a wrong prediction. If a broader category is predicted rather than the most exact category, in this version the prediction was still counted as being true. This is the most pragmatic model and its result is, what would most likely be presented to the VIVO user.

Figure 8: Classification results of applying a machine learning model to 19.000 research documents.

Next Steps

Technology can help us model, connect, and classify research projects and outputs, yet technology still has its limits. The quality and magnitude of available datasets affect the classification precision. The smaller the dataset or the more unbalanced it is, the more challenging the classification process becomes. Those challenges can be compensated with large amounts of training data leading to a precise prediction model.

Even though it is precise, the model needs to measure up against real world data and inconsistencies are bound to happen. We therefore suggest an update scheme to improve the quality of the classification

results, as shown in Figure 9. It starts with the pre-classification as discussed above. Neural models are then trained on its basis and an initial classification is calculated. The results will be imported into the VIVO platform, and linked into the existing ontologies. Those changes will be visible to end-users instantly.

Experts, more specifically the authors of the classified articles, project descriptions and other texts, will be given the opportunity to inspect and curate the classification. Corrections will automatically be re-imported into the classification software, are used to retrain the model and to improve the accuracy of further classifications. Updates should be triggered regularly to enhance the classification shown on the VIVO platform. Manually input data will be given priority over modeled data. This update loop will go on indefinitely, ensuring that every correction leads to a stronger prediction model and in turn to more precise data shown to users.

We need supportive efforts with the researchers and the scientific community as a whole for approving and potentially correcting the classification results of their own work. An iterated, cooperative approach can lead to robust classification of research outputs that are published on the whole platform and across platforms. Linking research outputs through ontologies will not only be the backbone of a strong search algorithm but will also allow to create a more useful and crucial visualizations than what VIVO is able to provide today.

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